

The impact of Business Process Outsourcing on Sustainable Competitive Advantage in the Financial Services Industry in Zimbabwe

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Abstract

Business process outsourcing (BPO) is a fairly new field within research in Zimbabwe. Most companies are in a bid to remain competitive within the financial services industry. The study sought to investigate the impact of BPO on sustainable competitive advantage in the financial services industry. The research adopted the positivism research philosophy which resulted in a quantitative research design. The data was analyzed using IBM SPSS bivariate correlation analysis. Raosoft calculator was used to determine the sample of 148 units from the target population of 240. The findings were that business process outsourcing has a direct relationship with sustainable competitive advantage. According to the results, innovation, highly capable IT teams and cost reduction were all a result of outsourcing of IT services. Accounting outsourcing, through the study, showed that it allowed companies to have access to expertise which are not available internally. It also showed that companies can focus on their core competencies whilst they outsource processes that can be done externally. The study suggested that the factors considered for sustainable competitive advantage are directly affected or impacted by outsourcing of services and processes. The study recommended that due diligence should be taken when implementing BPO. It also recommended that cost-benefit analysis and risk assessment be carried out before deciding on whether to outsource or not.

Keywords: *Business Process Outsourcing, Competitive, sustainable competitive advantage, financial services, cost benefit analysis.*

Suggested citation: Senga, T., Senga, T., & Simuka, J. (2024). The impact of Business Process Outsourcing on Sustainable Competitive Advantage in the Financial Services Industry in Zimbabwe. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 1(1), 52-69. DOI: 10.59324/ejmecb.2024.1(1).05

Introduction

Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) is the strategic initiative of subcontracting non-core business operations to external service providers to improve efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance overall company performance (Fattouch et. all, 2022). Subsequently a company attains a sustainable

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competitive advantage through BPO when it implements different strategies that places it ahead of competitors' moves (Bogers, Chesbrough, Heaton, & Teece, 2019). Sustainable competitive advantage is when a company implements different strategies that result in them being unpredictable or misleading competitors to overcome competitors' moves (Bogers, Chesbrough, Heaton, & Teece, 2019). This results in the company implementing a value-creating strategy not simultaneously being implemented by any of its competitors. Outsourcing of business support functions such as Human Resource Operational activities, finance and accounting, Information technology (IT), sales, and marketing allows businesses to focus on core business activities essential for the growth of the organization (Austin-Egole & Iheriohanma, 2020). As the global economy is increasingly becoming more competitive, there is an increased need for crafting strategies to differentiate service offerings from competitors (Rust, 2020). The rising focus of enterprises on improving efficiency, organizations' agility, reducing operating costs, and concentrating on core capabilities drive the growth of business process outsourcing (Omoile, 2020). These aspects have encouraged the adoption of BPO services across several industries. In developed countries, outsourcing has been adopted to maintain a competitive advantage in both core activities and non-core activities (Laktionova et al., 2022). Companies in these countries outsource activities to entities that specialize in the areas, for example, financial management and financial accounting. The study sought to determine the impact of outsourcing IT services, Call center services and Human Resources in relation to company performance in the financial services industry.

Literature Review

The Concept of Business Process Outsourcing

Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) was defined by Fattouch et al. (2022) as the strategic effort of subcontracting non-core business functions to external service providers to improve efficiency, reduce costs, and improve overall company performance. Opuene and Ejo-orusa (2020) defined BPO as the practice of entrusting previously integrated transactions to an external supplier under a long-term contract. Krysińska et al. (2018), BPO is the practice of outsourcing a task that was previously undertaken internally. It entails handing over control of the activity's design, management, and development to a dependable third-party service provider. Shi (2022) on the other hand, characterized business process outsourcing as a strategic choice that requires engaging better capacity firms externally to handle particular non-core activities or processes that are necessary.

Organizations generally have three different types of business processes: core processes that provide a strategic advantage; critical non-core processes that are important but do not provide a competitive advantage; and non-core non-critical processes that are required to maintain the environment (Kulangara et al., 2022). By carefully utilizing outside contractors to provide formerly internal operations services, businesses may concentrate their time and resources on key capabilities (Austin-Egole & Iheriohanma, 2020). Operations for business process outsourcing may be divided into three categories: Sales, marketing, and customer service (such as customer analytics, customer acquisition, and customer retention); supply chain management (such as direct procurement, warehouse/inventory, transportation & logistics); and business administration (such as general administration, finances, human resources, and payment services) (Igbatayo, 2019).

The Concept of Sustainable Competitive Advantage (SCA)

The SCA is considered to be when a company has a superior position. or condition over a competitor over. a long period by reacting to the world's never-ending changes (Mahdi & Nassar, 2021). Competitive advantage .is a concept that remains a prominent research field in strategic management (Farida & Setiawan, 2022). In addition, they added, "A firm that earns superior.

financial returns within its sector or market, over the long run, is said to have a competitive advantage over competitors". Strategic senior managers' primary pre-work in competitive and slow-growth markets is to gain a competitive advantage. A company has a competitive advantage if it is implementing a value-creating strategy that no current or potential competitors are using at the same time. When other companies are unable to replicate the benefits of this strategy, they can confirm that the company has SCA. Temporary and sustainable competitive advantages exist (Nohong et al., 2018). They claim that while competitive advantage usually results in significant profits, these profits attract competitors, and that competition, in most cases, limits the duration of competitive advantage. As a result, even the most significant competitive advantage is fleeting. According to Kuncoro and Suriani (2018), some competitive advantages can be sustained if competitors cannot duplicate the source of advantage or if no competitor can think of a superior.

Theoretical framework

Core Competences Theory

The concept of core competency states that "organizations must play to their strengths or those areas or functions in which they have competence" (Essien & Bassey, 2020). A company's distinguishing features or talents must be visible to set it apart from its competitors. The core competency argument states that a company should keep performing its basic business responsibilities (Chris & Lucky 2021). According to Grewal et. al. (2021), core competencies and BPO are related in three ways. Firstly, BPO can be used to free up internal resources so that companies can focus on their core competencies. For example, a company that outsources its IT functions can free up its internal IT staff to focus on developing new products and services. Secondly, BPO can be used to access expertise in specialized areas that companies may not have in-house. For example, a company that outsources its customer service functions can access the expertise of a customer service provider that specializes in that area. Thirdly, BPO can be used to scale up or down business operations quickly and easily, which can be helpful for companies with dynamic core competencies Grewal et. al. (2021). Whilst BPO can support a company in maintaining its core competencies, some challenges can be faced (Chernysh et al., 2018). Identification of the right business processes to be outsourced can be a challenge. Careful considerations should be made when identifying which processes are essential to core competencies and which processes can be outsourced without affecting a company's competitive advantage (Grechyskin, 2019). Another challenge is the selection of the right outsourcing provider. A company should thoroughly evaluate the provider's expertise, track record, and financial stability. Proper due diligence should be carried out and ensure that the provider is aligned with the company's core values and culture.

Transaction Cost Economics Theory

Transaction cost economics (TCE) theory is a theory that explains how companies make decisions about whether to produce goods and services in-house or to outsource them to external providers. TCE theory posits that companies will outsource goods and services to external providers when the transaction costs of outsourcing are lower than the transaction costs of producing the goods and services in-house. According to Andow et al. (2018), TCE theory provides a framework for cost allocation in outsourcing. TCE theory posits that companies will outsource goods and services to external providers when the transaction costs of outsourcing are lower than the transaction costs of producing the goods and services in-house. This means that when a firm actively outsources portions of a business unit or function, the cost of such activities is reduced and shifted to the outsourced company, improving organizational performance (Ndiiri & Kilika, 2021). Many believe that transaction cost economics provides the best decision-making tools that organizations can employ in determining whether to outsource and to plan for potential outsourcing agreements (Ezezue et al., 2019). Transaction costs, according to the TCE theory, are influenced by different

factors. The complexity of processes being outsourced plays a major role in determining the cost of the outsourced service or process (Ketokivi & Mahoney, 2020). Another factor is the availability of outsourcing providers in the market for the specific business process to be outsourced. This also has an impact on the pricing of the outsourced process. Level of specificity and uncertainty are also factors that influence the cost of outsourcing a process.

Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

The resource-based view is regarded as one of the most prominent ideas in management research history, particularly in terms of strategic management deployment (Mahdi & Nassar, 2021). According to the RBV, organizations are essentially composed of specific resources. RBV assumes that a company's assets are its resources and that its competitive advantage is dependent on its resources and strategic skills. Resources are classified as tangible or intangible (Khan et al., 2020). Tangible resources are physical characteristics that are simple to manage and control, thereby increasing productivity. Intangible resources, on the other hand, are soft resources such as human intelligence, innovation, company reputation, quality service, and products. According to this view, if companies have resources with valuable, scarce, unrepeatable, and irreplaceable features, they have a sustainable competitive advantage. If they have only valuable and scarce features, they have a temporary SCA (Onjewu et al., 2022). Researchers have considered RBV in various areas, such as entrepreneurship, marketing, international trade, and strategic management (Venkatesan, 2022). Numerous studies of RBV indicate that intangible resources are identified as the most likely resource of SCA (Malik et al., 2023). The RBV's basic concept is to use the company's resources, particularly internal sources, and core competencies to develop SCA, which leads to improved performance (Mishra et al., 2018). The RBV stresses an organization's distinct assets and competencies that make the difference in gaining a competitive advantage. The RBV's basic concept is to use the company's resources, particularly internal sources, and core competencies to develop SCA, which leads to improved performance (Mishra et al., 2018). The RBV stresses an organization's distinct assets and competencies that make the difference in gaining a competitive advantage. As a result, management efforts should be directed at gathering, developing, and exploiting these strategic resources to maintain a competitive advantage.

The Impact of Outsourcing IT Services on Company Performance

Outsourcing of IT services (ITO) denotes the use of specific components within the service provider structure that contribute to the customer's IT infrastructure (Kamalaldin et al., 2020). Recent research has argued that to achieve long-term performance, organizations should abandon short-term, cost-focused models (Ancarani et al., 2022). This new emphasis on innovation, rather than cost-only models, enables both outsourcing clients and suppliers to overcome self-interest. This changes the client-supplier relationship into a "win-win" partnership that can potentially achieve both efficiency and innovation while allowing both parties to achieve long-term performance (i.e., sustainable performance) (Chukwuogor et al., 2021). Their goal is to increase efficiency by leveraging suppliers' skills, knowledge, and capabilities. This can be accomplished through ITO, in which suppliers provide firms with exceptional solutions that will set them apart in the market, resulting in innovation and efficiency.

The Impact of Human Resources Outsourcing on Company Performance

Human Resources Outsourcing (HRO) is the practice of contracting out certain HR functions to a third-party provider (Sakib et al., 2023). This can include a wide range of tasks, such as payroll, benefits administration, recruiting, and training. HRO has become increasingly popular in recent years, as businesses seek to reduce costs, improve efficiency, and focus on their core competencies. Studies have examined the motivations for outsourcing, the benefits, and risks of HRO, and the factors that contribute to success. Companies outsource HR functions for a variety of reasons. The

most common reasons are Cost reduction, improved efficiency, Access to expertise, and Scalability (Sakib et. al., 2023). On cost reduction, HRO aids companies to reduce costs by eliminating the need to hire and train their HR staff. Outsourcing can free up internal HR staff to focus on more strategic initiatives thereby improving their efficiency. With HRO, companies can have access to expertise in specialized HR areas, such as global payroll and benefits administration. Outsourcing can also help companies to scale their HR operations up or down quickly and easily. Guenther (2020) asserts that HRO is becoming increasingly complex. He argues that the range of HR functions that are being outsourced is expanding, and the relationships between companies and their outsourcing providers are becoming more complex (Guenther, 2020). Another challenge HRO is facing is cybersecurity threats hence the need to comply with complex global regulations (Guenther, 2020). Other researchers have opined that companies are increasingly using HRO to support strategic goals such as global expansion and digital transformation (Davenport et al., 2019). To support digital transformation, according to Davenport et al. (2019), HRO providers are using data analytics to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of HR processes.

The Impact of Outsourcing Accounting Services on Company Performance

Accounting outsourcing is the practice of contracting out accounting functions to an external service provider (Malik et. al., 2023). Accounting outsourcing can be used to reduce costs, improve efficiency, and access expertise in specialized areas. Accounting functions can include bookkeeping, accounts payable, accounts receivable, payroll, tax preparation, and financial reporting (Chorna et al. 2019). Benefits associated with accounting outsourcing are reduced costs, improved efficiency, access to expertise and companies can focus on their core business (Tomašević et al., 2023). Accounting costs may be reduced by eliminating the need to hire and train in-house accounting staff. In terms of efficiency, outsourcing can help in providing expertise that is not readily available in-house, for example, tax experts. However, according to Gulin et. al. (2019), there are challenges associated with outsourcing of accounting services and these include loss of control over the quality and accuracy of their accounting data and security concerns regarding exposing accounting information to external or third-party companies. However strict measures should be put in place to ensure that providers only access what they are supposed to.

The Impact of Call Center Outsourcing on Customer Service Quality

Call center outsourcing is the practice of contracting out call center operations to a third-party provider Garg & Garg (2020). This can include a wide range of tasks, such as customer service, sales, and technical support. Call center outsourcing has become increasingly popular in recent years, as businesses seek to reduce costs, improve efficiency, and access global talent. In recent years, there has been a growing body of research on call center outsourcing. Call center outsourcing is becoming more complex. According to Garg & Garg (2020), the range of call center services that are being outsourced is expanding, and the relationships between companies and their outsourcing providers are becoming more complex. They also asserted that due to the hosting of call center infrastructure, there is a high risk of cyber security threats. Grewal et al. (2021), opined that for call center outsourcing to be successful companies need to ensure careful consideration when choosing the outsourcing company. They also advise that there should be a clear definition of roles and responsibilities as well as a clear communication plan with the outsourcing service provider.

Conceptual Framework (Figure 1)

Based on the conceptual framework, the following hypothesis are proposed:

H1 Outsourcing of IT services has a positive impact on company performance

H2 Outsourcing of Call center has a positive impact on customer service quality

H3 Human resources outsourcing has a positive impact on company performance

H4 Accounting services outsourcing has a positive impact on cost reduction.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Materials and Methods

The study adopted the positivisim research philosophy. Comte (2019) defines positivism as a philosophical school of thought that emphasizes the use of quantifiable facts and empirical observation in comprehending the natural and social worlds. In the context of research, positivism is a philosophical stance that views the process as an objective and methodical undertaking to identify universal laws and causal linkages through the collection of empirical data (Gordon, 2022). The study's quantitative research methodology was supported by the positivist research philosophy, which was used to investigate the effects of business process outsourcing (BPO) on sustainable organizational competitive advantage in the financial services industry. The population used in the research was 240, which comprised of employees from the head office of financial institutions in Harare, Zimbabwe. The decision to focus on the employees at the head office is that the head office represents the central hub of the organization where key decision-making processes and strategic activities take place and by focusing on a specific location, such as the head office, it becomes more feasible to collect data and conduct the study within the given resource and time constraints. The manageable size of the population ensures that data collection and analysis can be conducted efficiently and effectively. Raosoft calculator was used to determine the sample size of 148 using a margin of error of $\pm 5\%$ at a 95% confidence level. Stratified sampling was used. According to Kothari (2019), Stratified sampling is a probability sampling method that involves dividing the population into distinct subgroups or strata based on specific characteristics. The decision to use stratified sampling was based on several reasons that is its heterogeneity within the population. The number of employees at the head office the companies chosen for the research may consist of individuals with diverse characteristics, such as different departments, job roles, or

levels of experience. By employing stratified sampling, the study aimed to ensure that each subgroup or stratum within the population is adequately represented in the sample.

The research made use of close ended questionnaires as a data collection method. This method allowed the researcher to collect primary data. For secondary data, the researcher made use of company reports to support the primary data. The decision to use questionnaires in the study was based on the following justification. SPSS version 29 was used in the research to analyze the data. Statistical analysis was used on the collected quantitative data to derive meaningful insights. Data was loaded onto SPSS for statistical analysis. Descriptive analytics were applied to show the distribution of respondents. Some common analyses include frequency analysis which involves determining the frequencies and percentages of responses to each question. It provided an understanding of the distribution of responses and the prevalence of certain attitudes or opinions. Measures such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were calculated to provide a clear overview of the responses to each question. These statistics allowed for a concise representation of the data, highlighting the central tendencies and variability. In terms of construct validity, the questionnaire design involved a thorough review of existing literature, consultation with experts, and pilot testing to refine and validate the measurement scales. To establish content validity, the questionnaire items were carefully developed to align with the research objectives and the theoretical framework. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated to assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire items. To address ethical considerations, participants were provided with clear and detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. All participants provided informed consent, ensuring their voluntary participation. Participants were informed of their rights to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. In addition, the participants' privacy and confidentiality were strictly maintained. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the data collection, analysis, and reporting phases of the study.

Results and Discussion

102 employees responded giving a response rate of 68.9%. A reliability analysis was carried out to check consistency on the data using Cronbach's alpha method. An overall coefficient of 0.728 was obtained to confirm the consistency of the data as shown below.

Table 1. Summary

		N.	%
Cases	Valid	95	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	95	100.0

Table 2. Reliability Statistic

	Cronbach's Alpha.	N of Items
IT Outsourcing	0.738	5
HR Outsourcing	0.710	4
Call Centre Outsourcing	0.700	5
Accounting Outsourcing	0.764	4
Overall score	0.728	18

Table 3. Demographics by Age

		Frequency.	Percent.	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Below 30 years	25	26.3	26.3	26.3
	31-40 years	31	32.6	32.6	58.9
	41-50 years	21	22.1	22.1	81.1
	51-60 years	18	18.9	18.9	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Table 4. Demographics by Gender

		Frequency.	Percent.	Valid %	Cumulative %.
Valid	Male	48	50.5	50.5	50.5
	Female	47	49.5	49.5	100.0
	Total	95	96.9	100.0	

Table 5. Demographics by Company Name

		Frequency	Percent	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	A	11	11.6	11.6	11.6
	B	37	38.9	38.9	50.5
	C	26	27.4	27.4	77.9
	D	11	11.6	11.6	89.5
	E	10	10.5	10.5	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Table 6. Demographics by Position

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Managerial	45	47.4	47.4	47.4
	Non-Managerial	50	52.6	52.6	100.0
	Total	95	100	100.0	

Table 7. Demographics by Educational Qualification

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Masters	29	30.5	30.5	30.5
	Bachelors	58	61.1	61.1	91.6
	Diploma	8	8.4	8.4	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Table 8. Demographics by Experience

Experience					
		Frequency	Percent %	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	0-10 years	61	64.2	64.2	64.2
	11-20 years	12	12.6	12.6	76.8
	Over 20 years	22	23.2	23.2	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Total sample was 148 and 64.2% responded to the questionnaire distributed. On Gender 50.5% of respondents were male according to the coding scale. 47.4% of respondents were of managerial level. This is significant for the study in that it helps get a perspective from decision makers with regards to competitive advantage. 61.1% of the respondents have at least a Bachelor's degree. Respondents with experience of 0-10 years within the financial services industry were 64.2%. This was helpful to the study as it allowed collection of data from people who have seen the implementation of BPO and its effects.

The impact of outsourcing IT services on company performance

Table 9. IT Outsourcing

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
IT Outsourcing	95	1.00	.000
IT process types	95	2.26	.656
Cost reduction	95	2.18	.772
IT department capability	95	2.16	.468
Innovation	95	2.05	.658
Valid N (listwise)	95		

From the results, the IT process types mean was 2.26 which implies that Software development is mainly being outsourced. A mean of 2.18 shows that respondents agree that outsourcing of IT reduces cost using the Likert scale that was used on the research instrument. IT Department capability and Innovation have means of 2.16 and 2.05 respectively implying that the IT departments are highly capable and there is Innovation among the teams. RBV theory assumes that a company's assets are its resources (Khan et al., 2020) and this contributes to its competitive advantage. As evidenced by the results, respondents agreed that their IT teams are highly capable, implying that they have the right skillset. Kamalaldin et al. (2020) stated that companies should leverage on existing Infrastructure by outsourcing companies to reduce costs. Ancarani et al., 2022 stated that organizations should aim to achieve long term goals through Innovation and this can be supported by the results where respondents agreed that Innovation is being promoted through outsourcing. This can be seen from the results that there is significant cost reduction. The results were further tested using Correlation to establish if the hypothesis can be accepted or rejected.

Table 10. Correlation IT Outsourcing

		IT process types	Cost reduction	Innovation	IT department capability
IT process types	Pearson Correlation	1	.453**	.239*	.383**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	0.02	<.001
	N	95	95	95	95
Cost reduction	Pearson Correlation	.453**	1	.295**	.362**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		0.004	<.001
	N	95	95	95	95
Innovation	Pearson Correlation	.239*	.295**	1	.318**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.02	0.004		0.002
	N	95	95	95	95
	Pearson Correlation	.383**	.362**	.318**	1
IT department capability	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	0.002	
	N	95	95	95	95

Note: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed); **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the correlation analysis, the variables had Pearson's correlation is significant at the 0.01 confidence interval which showed that there is a significant relationship between IT Outsourcing and sustainable competitive advantage. There is also a significant correlation at the 0.05 confidence level. Essien & Bassey (2020) state that a company should focus on its core competencies. From the results, Innovation and IT resources capability is shown to be prevalent. This confirms the assertion made by Essien & Bassey (2020) as the employees are able to focus on what they do best and have other functions outsourced. Cost reduction allows companies to have improved performance. As Farida & Setiawan (2022) stated, organizations with high performance are more likely to attain a sustainable competitive advantage. Hence one can note that through Innovation and cost reduction, a company can attain high performance which leads to sustainable competitive advantage. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

The questions asked were to determine the type of IT services being outsourced. The respondents agreed that Software development is mainly being outsourced. Each organization has its own set of IT services that they outsource due to several reasons. The bigger organizations outsource fewer services due to the availability of resources within their teams. They, however, outsource software development. Further research on secondary data showed that these services are outsourced mainly from service providers external to Zimbabwe. However, for the other organizations they outsource services including IT audit, Helpdesk and Infrastructure. This is due to the unavailability of resources within the organization. For IT infrastructure, there is a need for huge capital injection for a company to setup standard infrastructure. The cost of setting up supersedes the cost of renting out already set up infrastructure from service providers for example TelOne.

The Impact of Human Resources Outsourcing on Company Performance

Table 11. HR Outsourcing

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Types of HR outsourcing	95	1.68	.570
Cost reduction	95	1.99	.273
Skills Improvement	95	1.79	.481
Increased morale	95	1.95	.590
Valid N (listwise)	95		

From the results, the types of HR processes mean was 1.68 which implies that Training Services and Recruitment Services are mainly being outsourced. A mean of 1.99 shows that respondents agree that outsourcing of HR services reduces cost using the Likert scale that was used on the research instrument. Skills improvement had a mean of 1.79 showing that respondents agree that there will be skills improvement. A mean of 1.79 shows that respondents agree that the morale of employees will be increased. RBV, according to Onjewu et al., 2022, states that in order to have SCA, companies should have valuable and scarce features. Increased morale and improves skillset contribute to valuable human resources. Training of resources enables the company to have resources with distinguished skillsets.

Table 12. Correlation HR Outsourcing

		Types of HR outsourcing	Cost reduction	Skills improvement	Increased morale
Types of HR outsourcing	Pearson Correlation	1	-.022	-.129	-.145
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.835	.214	.161
	N	95	95	95	95
Cost reduction	Pearson Correlation	-.022	1	.064	-.070
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.835		.538	.503
	N	95	95	95	95
Skills improvement	Pearson Correlation	-.129	.064	1	.298**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.214	.538		.003
	N	95	95	95	95
Increased morale	Pearson Correlation	-.145	-.070	.298**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.161	.503	.003	
	N	95	95	95	95

Note: ** correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

From the results the correlation is significant at the 0.01 confidence interval. This shows that there is a significant relationship among the variables. Training enables employees to gain more knowledge whereas recruitment done from outside helps with cost cutting and allows organizations to get the best talent in the market. According to Andow et al. (2018), TCE theory states that companies will outsource goods and services to external providers when the transaction costs of outsourcing are lower than the transaction costs of producing the goods and services in-house. This means that when a firm actively outsources portions of a business unit or function, the cost of such activities is reduced and shifted to the outsourced company, improving organizational performance (Ndiiri & Kilika, 2021). This implies that companies who attain cost reduction have a positive impact on their performance thereby promoting sustainable competitive advantage. This concludes that the hypothesis is accepted.

The Impact of Outsourcing Accounting Services on Company Performance

Table 13. Accounting Outsourcing

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Accounting processes	95	1.86	.518
Reduced Costs	95	2.00	.601
Efficiency	95	1.92	.539
Expertise	95	1.66	.497
Valid N (listwise)	95		

The results in the table of a mean of 1.86 on accounting processes show that respondents agree that Tax and advisory services are mainly outsourced. Costs have a mean of 2 showing that respondents agree that there are reduced costs due to outsourcing/ Efficiency and expertise both have means of 1.92 and 1.66 respectively showing that respondents agree that there is increased efficiency and access to expertise. Access to expertise provides internal staff to focus on their core business as alluded to by Tomašević et al. (2023). By focusing on core tasks, the employees' productivity is increased resulting in an increase in company performance. This is further tested by correlation analysis as shown in the following table.

Table 14. Correlations Accounting

		Accounting processes	Reduced costs	Efficiency	Expertise
Accounting processes	Pearson Correlation	1	.512**	.339**	.191
	Sig. (2 - tailed)		<.001	<.001	.064
	N	95	95	95	95
Reduced costs	Pearson Correlation	.512**	1	.328**	.285**
	Sig. (2 - tailed)	<.001		.001	.005
	N	95	95	95	95
Efficiency	Pearson Correlation	.339**	.328**	1	.330**
	Sig. (2 - tailed)	<.001	.001		.001
	N	95	95	95	95
Expertise	Pearson Correlation	.191	.285**	.330**	1
	Sig. (2 - tailed)	.064	.005	.001	
	N	95	95	95	95

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation is significant at the 0.01 confidence interval implying that there is a significant relationship between the variables. This shows that there is a correlation among variables. It implies that outsourcing of accounting services has a direct relationship with competitive advantage. Hence one can say that the hypothesis is accepted.

The questions main aim was to find out the impact of outsourcing within the accounting department. Cost reduction, Efficiency and access to expertise were used as factors within the questions. Respondents agreed that due to outsourcing, costs were significantly reduced. These could be costs of hiring permanent accounting resources. Efficiency was also noted as respondents agreed that outsourcing led to efficiency within the department. This is due to resources being able to focus on their core tasks. To understand this further a question was asked to check the types of services being outsourced in the accounting department. Respondents agreed that Tax and Advisory services were being outsourced. This is a function that is crucial although it can be done through outsourcing. Access to expertise is another factor that was asked in the research. It was noted outsourcing accounting services enhances access to expertise as there are other expertise that are not normally found within organizations. All these factors are said to be contributing to competitiveness of a company.

The Impact of Call Center Outsourcing on Customer Service Quality

Table 15. Call Centre Outsourcing

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Call Center outsourcing	95	1.63	.485
Efficiency	95	2.56	.578
Customer Rating	95	2.51	.599
Acceptance of products	95	2.59	.592
Communication	95	2.29	.921
Valid N (list wise)	95		

From the results a mean of 1.63 shows that respondents agree that their organizations outsource call center services. Respondents are neutral on the Efficiency of call Centre providers which can be seen by a mean of 2.56. The respondents are also neutral on the Customer rating and acceptance of products. However, it can be noted that respondents agree that the providers communicate well. Further test of correlation were done on the data as shown in the following table.

Table 16. Correlations Call Centre

Correlations Call Centre		Call Centre outsourcing	Efficiency	Customer Rating	Acceptance of products	Communication
Call Centre outsourcing	Pearson Correlation	1	.741**	.684**	.616**	.841**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	95	95	95	95	95
Efficiency	Pearson Correlation	.741**	1	.805**	.707**	.846**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	95	95	95	95	95
Customer Rating	Pearson Correlation	.684**	.805**	1	.710**	.787**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	95	95	95	95	95
Acceptance of products	Pearson Correlation	.616**	.707**	.710**	1	.731**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	95	95	95	95	95
Communication	Pearson Correlation	.841**	.846**	.787**	.731**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	95	95	95	95	95

The results show that there is significant relationship between outsourcing and Efficiency, customer rating, acceptance of products and communication. This shows that there is a linear relationship among variables. Hence one can conclude that the hypothesis is accepted.

The researcher, in a bid to understand whether the companies were outsourcing their call centre services, asked the question if they were outsourcing. The respondents agreed that their organizations are outsourcing call Centre services. Another question was asked to check the efficiency of Call centre providers. The respondents agreed that customer issues are responded to in a timely manner. This shows that there is efficiency in attending to customer queries. For outsourcing contracts to be effective, there needs to be clearly defined roles and communication protocols According to Garg & Garg (2020), the range of call centre services that are being outsourced is expanding, and the relationships between companies and their outsourcing providers are becoming more complex hence the need to have proper agreements and SLAs. The researcher posed a question to find out if service providers are effectively communicating and providing feedback from customers. From the data collected, respondents agreed that their service providers communicated effectively providing feedback from customers.

Summary of Findings

The Impact of Outsourcing IT Services on Company Performance in the Financial Services Industry

The results show that most employees agree that there is Innovation, cost reduction, high capability of IT resources due to outsourcing. The capability of IT resources is also influenced by outsourcing. Resources leverage on the expertise of external service providers to gain knowledge and improve their skills. The correlation analysis further confirms that there is a significant relationship between outsourcing and competitive advantage. The significant correlation led to the conclusion that the hypothesis that IT Outsourcing has a positive impact on sustainable competitive advantage be accepted.

The Impact of Outsourcing Call Centre Services on Customer Service Quality

The researcher, in a bid to understand whether the companies were outsourcing their call centre services and the impact in service quality, four questions were presented to the respondents Customer service satisfaction rating, communication, timely response to customers were included in gathering the data. Respondents agreed that the Call Centre providers communicate effectively. On the other hand, respondents remained neutral on customers rating their companies highly, Efficiency and acceptance of products. The correlation analysis showed a significant relationship between outsourcing and competitive advantage hence the hypothesis is accepted.

The Impact of HR Outsourcing Services on Company Performance

The researcher, in a bid to understand whether outsourcing had an effect on skills improvement and employee morale, questions were asked on the types of processes being outsourced, how skills and morale have improved. The respondents agreed that Training and Recruitment are being outsourced mostly. The respondents noted that there was increased morale and improved skills due to outsourcing of these processes. Another question was asked to check if there was cost reduction, and it was noted that indeed outsourcing reduced costs of operations within the HR departments.

The Impact of Accounting Services Outsourcing on Company Performance

The researcher formulated questions to find out the impact of outsourcing within the accounting department. Cost reduction, Efficiency and access to expertise were used as factors within the questions. Respondents agreed that due to outsourcing, costs were significantly reduced. These could be costs of hiring permanent accounting resources. Efficiency was also noted as respondents agreed that outsourcing led to efficiency within the department. This is due to resources being able to focus on their core tasks. To understand this further a question was asked to check the types of services being outsourced in the accounting department. Respondents agreed that Tax and Advisory services were being outsourced. This is a function that is crucial although it can be done through outsourcing. Access to expertise is another factor that was asked in the research. It was noted outsourcing accounting services enhances access to expertise as there are other expertise that are not normally found within organizations. All these factors are said to be contributing to competitiveness of a company.

Conclusion

This research has revealed the factors of IT outsourcing and how they impact sustainable competitive advantage. The major findings of the study point towards some common factors on processes which influence sustainable competitive advantage. As the study was concentrated

companies within the financial services industry, the results have shown that mainly Software development is being outsourced.

Call centre services is one of the outsourcing services that was accepted well within Zimbabwe. The research showed that most of the companies under study were outsourcing these services. This also gives them room to focus on their key competencies whilst they have a competent provider handling customer queries. One can argue that any organization needs to be in touch with their customers hence outsourcing call centre deviates the organization from doing so. However, if proper due diligence is carried out and expectations are set, then the outsourcing becomes a success. Trends as seen from empirical reviews is that there are measures being put in place to mitigate the risks that might be associated with call centre outsourcing.

The study concluded that outsourcing of HR services has a positive impact on SCA. It was noted that employee morale and skills improved due to outsourcing of services like training. It was also noted that costs were reduced due to outsourcing. Recruitment services is another factor that was supported in the study. This may be due to the large pool of skilled human resources that are outside the organizations. The organizations are recruiting externally to bring in new knowledge.

Accounting processes or services are extremely sensitive within the financial services sector. However, the study has shown that Tax and advisory services are mainly being outsourced. Tax and advisory experts are limited and might be expensive to hire hence outsourcing these services helps with cost reduction. This also allows for the accounting departments to focus on their key performance areas.

Recommendations

Due to digitalization, it is recommended that companies look into outsourcing more processes and services for example Infrastructure Services or hosting services. Whilst there are security concerns within the industry, the service providers have put in place many measures to mitigate the risks associated. Further research can be done to ascertain the differences in cost of outsourcing and the cost of setting up the infrastructure. This will aid in decision making. Thorough cost benefit analysis maybe done to ascertain whether the benefits outweigh the costs.

In order for companies to select the right service provider, proper due diligence should be carried out. Checks should be made to see if the providers' culture and values align with the companies' culture. When contracting, proper and clear expectations should be set, to ensure outsourcing becomes a success. Trends as seen from empirical reviews is that there are measures being put in place to mitigate the risks that might be associated with call centre outsourcing. However, it is recommended that any company within the financial services industry should do a proper due diligence and analysis before considering engaging an outsourcing provider.

It is recommended that due caution is taken when recruiting externally. Recruitment service provider should understand well the companies' culture and values in order for them to select candidates that align. If due care is not takes, candidates that do not resonate with company culture and values will be recruited and this may pose several challenges.

It is recommended that when outsourcing accounting services, proper risk assessment should be taken. Cost benefit analysis of outsourcing the services should also be done. Thorough analysis of processes to be outsourced needs to be done.

References

- Ancarani, A., Di Mauro, C., & Gitto, S. (2022). An empirical analysis of the profitability of backshoring initiatives to Europe. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 33(8), 1385–1406. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jmtm-03-2022-0101>
- Andow, A. A., Dabo, Z., & Ejeh, E. C. (2018). Impact of outsourcing on organizational performance of listed food and beverages firms in Nigeria. *LASU Journal of Employment Relations & Human Resource Management*, 1(1), 156–166. <https://doi.org/10.36108/ljerhrm/8102.01.0181>
- Austin-Egole, I.S. & Iheriohanma, E.B.J. (2020). Outsourcing and Organizational Performance: A Comparative Analysis of Nigeria Bottling Company Plant and Camela Vegetable Oil Company, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities & Social Sciences*, 10(1), 64– 83.
- Bogers, M., Chesbrough, H., Heaton, S., & Teece, D. J. (2019). Strategic management of open innovation: A dynamic capabilities perspective. *California Management Review*, 62(1), 77–94
- Chernysh, I., Glebova, A., & Maksymenko, O. (2018). Business Processes Outsourcing in Building Enterprises. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(3.2), 59. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i3.2.14376>
- Chorna, Maryna, Anzhelika Krutova, Liliya Filipishyna, Lyubov Bezghinova, and Olena Drobysheva. 2019. Features of the evaluation of the effectiveness of anti-crisis entrepreneurship in industry. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 22, 1–8
- Chris, B., & Lucky, O. (2021). In-Country Outsourcing and Employment Parties in the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry. *The International Journal of Business & Management*, 9(8). <https://doi.org/10.24940/theijbm/2021/v9/i8/bm2108-034>
- Chukwuogor, C., Anoruo, E., & Ndu, I. (2021). An empirical analysis of the determinants of the U.S. banks' profitability. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 16(4), 209–217. [https://doi.org/10.21511/bbs.16\(4\).2021.17](https://doi.org/10.21511/bbs.16(4).2021.17)
- Ezezue, B.O., Ujebu, N., Nwekpa, K.C., Arisi, N.E. & Ulo, F. (2019). Impact of Outsourcing on Productivity in Bakery Industry, Abakaliki Metropolis. *IDOSR Journal of Arts & Management*, 4(2), 98–104.
- Farida, I., & Setiawan, D. (2022). Business Strategies and Competitive Advantage: The Role of Performance and Innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(3), 163. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8030163>
- Fattouch, N., Ben Lahmar, I., Rekik, M., & Boukadi, K. (2022) Decision-Making Approach for an IoRT-Aware Business Process Outsourcing. *Digital*, 2, 520–537.
- Garg, S., & Garg, R. (2020). Call center outsourcing: A comprehensive review of the literature. *International Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 10(1), 1–14
- Grechyshkin, Y. (2019, September 4). Increasing business process results in it-outsourcing enterprises. *Management*, 29(1), 130–142. <https://doi.org/10.30857/2415-3206.2019.1.11>
- Gulin, Danimir, Mirjana Hladika, and Ivana Valenta. (2019). Digitalization and the Challenges for the Accounting Profession. *Entrenova-Enterprise Research Innovation*, 5, 428–37
- Jaakkola, E. (2020). Designing conceptual articles: four approaches. *AMS Review*, 10(1–2), 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13162-020-00161-0>
- Kamalaldin, A., Linde, L., Sjödin, D., & Parida, V. (2020). Transforming provider-customer relationships in digital servitization: A relational view on digitalization. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 89, 306–325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2020.02.004>

- Ketokivi, M., & Mahoney, J. T. (2020). Transaction Cost Economics As a Theory of Supply Chain Efficiency. *Production and Operations Management*, 29(4), 1011–1031. <https://doi.org/10.1111/poms.13148>
- Krysińska, J., Janaszekiewicz, P., Prys, M., & Rózewski, P. (2018). Knowledge Resources Development Process In Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) Organizations. *Procedia Computer Science*, 126, 1145–1153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.08.052>
- Kulangara, N. P., Biehl, M., & Prater, E. L. (2022). Environmentally sustainable development initiatives in upstream strategic outsourcing relationships: Examining the role of innovative capabilities. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(7), 3014–3027. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3061>
- Laktionova, O., Kovalenko, Y., Myhovich, T., & Zharikova, O. (2022). Transforming Financial Outsourcing Services for Sustainable Business Development: A Review on Green Finance. *Economics. Ecology. Socium*, 6(4), 37–50. <https://doi.org/10.31520/2616-7107/2022.6.4-4>
- Mahdi, O. R., Nassar, I. A. (2021). The Business Model of Sustainable Competitive Advantage through Strategic Leadership Capabilities and Knowledge Management Processes to Overcome COVID-19 Pandemic. *Sustainability*, 13(17), 9891. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13179891>
- Malik, M., Ali, M., Latan, H., & Chiappetta Jabbour, C. J. (2023). Green project management practices, green knowledge acquisition, and sustainable competitive advantage: empirical evidence. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 27(9), 2350–2375. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jkm-06-2022-0466>
- Mishra, D., Kumar, S., Sharma, R., & Dubey, R. (2018). Outsourcing decision: do strategy and structure matter? *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 31(1), 26–46. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jocm-04-2017-0144>
- Nanjundeswaraswamy, T. S., & Divakar, S. (2021). Determination of sample size and sampling methods in applied research. *Proceedings on Engineering Sciences*, 3(1), 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.24874/pes03.01.003>
- Ndiiri, A., & Kilika, J. (2021). Business Process Outsourcing and Firm Performance of Selected Real Estate Firms in Nairobi City County, Kenya. *International Journal of Business Management, Entrepreneurship, and Innovation*, 3(3), 139–150. <https://doi.org/10.35942/jbmed.v3i3.221>
- Nohong, M., Sanusi, A., Nurqamar, I. F., & Harun, S. (2018). Strategic Model in Increasing the SME's Competitive Advantage in South Sulawesi. *Bisnis & Birokrasi Journal*, 25(2). <https://doi.org/10.20476/jbb.v25i2.9826>
- Omoile, P. (2020). Outsourcing Strategies and Organisational Performance of Chevron Nigeria Limited between 1999 and 2013. *SAU Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 5(1), 155-165
- Onjewu, A. K., Sadraei, R., & Jafari-Sadeghi, V. (2022). A bibliometric analysis of obesity in marketing research. *EuroMed Journal of Business*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/emjb-03-2022-0051>
- Rust, R.T. (2020). The future of marketing. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 37(1), 15-26
- Sakib, M. N., Tabassum, F., & Uddin, D. M. M. (2023). What we know about the trends, prospects, and challenges of human resource outsourcing: A systematic literature review. *Heliyon*, 9(8), e19018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19018>
- Saunders, M. N. K., Thornhill, A., & Lewis, P. (2019, January 1). *Research Methods for Business Students*.
- Shi, L. (2022). Strategic outsourcing's role in driving economic value by examining the mediating role of organizational capabilities and sustainable innovation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.933507>

Tomašević, I., Đurović, S., Abramović, N., Weis, L., & Koval, V. (2023). Factors Influencing Accounting Outsourcing Using the Transaction Cost Economics Model. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 11(2), 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs11020061>

Venkatesan, R. (2022). Sustainable Competitive Advantage. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4014642>

